

mated by

$$T_{opt} = -\frac{b}{2c}$$

The starting temperature was calculated by

$$T_{start} = T_{opt} - \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2c}$$

The coefficients of correlation (r) between root number and temperature level were 0.980** for Yuan Feng-Zao, 0.977** for Guang Lu-Ai No. 4, 0.933* for Er Jiu-Qing, and 0.973* for 776. The optimum temperatures for root number were 29.6° C for Yuan Feng-Zao, 27.7° C for Guang Lu-ai No. 4, 29.9° C for Er Jiu Qing, and 28.8° C for 776.

The T_{opt} for Guang Lu-Ai No. 4, is the lowest for all four varieties, which may indicate its relatively stronger resistance to low temperature. The result also indicates that each rice variety has an optimal temperature level that enhances seedling root number. A lower or higher temperature than this optimum reduces root number.

Root dry weights showed similar trends. The T_{opt} for root dry weight of 4 varieties were 29.9° C for Er Jiu-Qing,

Root number of rice seedlings and temperature at Shanghai.

29.7° C for Yuan Feng-Zao, 29.6° C for 776, and 27.5° C for Guang Lu-ai No. 4. The relationship between root length and temperature was quadratic, the coefficients of correlation (r) between root dry weight and temperature were 0.978 for 776, 0.960 for Yuan Feng-Zao, and 0.902 for Er Jiu-Qing. The correlation coefficient for Guang Lu-Ai No. 4 was not significant.

The minimum temperature for root number and root dry weight were

17.7° C and 17.9° C (mean 17.1° C) for Er Jiu-Qing, 15.8° C and 18.3° C (mean 17.1° C) for Yuan Feng-Zao, 16.5° C and 19.0° C (mean 17.8° C) for 776, and 14.9° C and 13.4° C (mean 14.2° C) for Guang Lu-Ai No. 4.

The mean daily optimum temperature during transplanting in the Shanghai area should be above 15° C for Guang Lu-ai No. 4, above 17° C for Yuan Feng-Zao, and above 18° C for Er Jiu-Qing and 776. ■

Effect of sowing date on sterility and vegetation period in western Turkey

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To assess the extent of cool temperature injury during anthesis, with special emphasis on sterility, varieties Kashmir Basmati, Krasnodorsky, Calrose,

Gritna, and Sarikilçik were sown in single rows of 50 plants each on 8 dates at 10-day intervals from 2 April to 11 June 1979. Plant spacing was 10 × 10 cm in 3 replications. Grains and sterile florets were counted separately.

The longest average vegetative period was 118 days (first sowing) and the shortest was 84 days (last sowing). Sarikilçik showed the shortest vegetative period and Calrose the longest (see table).

Average floret sterility was lowest in the second sowing date crop and highest in the last. Among varieties, Basmati showed the lowest sterility in its fourth sowing date and Krasnodorsky the highest in its seventh sowing date. A significant sowing date-variety interaction on sterility is shown in the table.

Temperature drastically affected sterility. Correlations between sterility and lowest temperature prevailing on the day

Effect of sowing date on days to heading (DH) and sterility of rice in western Turkey.

Sowing date ^a	Sarikilçik		Krasnodorsky		Calrose		Gritna		Kashmir Basmati		Average	
	DH	Sterility (%)	DH	Sterility (%)	DH	Sterility (%)	DH	Sterility (%)	DH	Sterility (%)	DH	Sterility (%)
1	107	20	107	18	142	23	121	25	112	16	118	20
2	103	14	103	15	130	14	115	17	111	16	112	15
3	94	15	104	17	122	22	108	19	102	14	106	17
4	86	28	94	18	114	11	105	40	119	10	104	22
5	84	21	82	31	110	13	99	19	111	17	97	20
6	82	32	80	39	101	11	96	37	102	18	92	27
7	82	29	75	55	94	13	90	22	94	16	87	27
8	77	35	76	41	89	22	80	36	93	19	84	31
Av	89	24	90	29	113	16	103	27	106	16	100	22.4

LSD: (for sterility % in arcsin transformation) for cultivar: (P: 0.05) = 1.55 for time: (P 0.05) = 1.90.

^a2 Apr-11 Jun 1979 at 10-day intervals.

of heading were -0.932 for Sarikilçik, -0.973 for Krasnodorsky, -0.907 for Calrose, -0.944 for Gritna, and -0.835 for Basmati. Correlations between sterility and the lowest temperature to which plants were exposed during the 11 days before heading (generally accepted as the starting point of microsporogenesis) were -0.608 for Sarikilçik, -0.863 for Krasnodorsky, -0.475 for Calrose, -0.630 for Gritna, and -0.012 for Basmati. Negative correlations for sterility-lowest temperature on heading day were higher than those for sterility-lowest temperature exposure during 11 days before heading. Even if there is no cool injury during microsporogenesis, a temperature below critical (15°C) within 12 hours of heading (on the day or night preceding heading) causes high sterility of florets. This may be due to indehiscence of anthers and failure of pollen grain germination on the stigma.

The response to critical temperature (15°C) varied from variety to variety. Krasnodorsky, Gritna, and Sarikilçik were affected more than Calrose and Basmati. Rice breeding programs in Turkey should concentrate on cool temperature injury during flowering for a second crop production model, which seems possible only with very early cultivars. ■

Cold-tolerant variety VLK Dhan 39 released for Uttar Pradesh hills

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Cold damage is the most serious constraint to rice yields in Northern India at altitudes up to 2200 meters. A highly cold-tolerant variety, VLK Dhan 39, recently was approved by the U.P. State Varietal Release Committee for cultivation in medium-altitude irrigated valleys.

VLK Dhan 39 — a pureline selection from China 1039/IR580-19-2-3-1, was isolated at Khudwani. It performed well in multilocational trials under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Programme. In 21 yield evaluation trials

Average yields for VLK Dhan 39 in Uttar Pradesh hills, India.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1976 (2)	1977 (6)	1978 (5)	1979 (7)	
VLK Dhan 39	3.0	4.7	3.7	2.3	3.4
Thapachini	2.2	3.4	2.7	2.1	2.6
Increase over Thapachini (%)		37.8	37.6	10.4	31.4

^aValues in parentheses indicate the number of sites where yields were averaged.

and farmers' field demonstrations, it outyielded the local check Thapachini by 31%.

VLK Dhan 39 is early-maturing (115 days) compared to local varieties (130 days). Plants are semi-tall with medium tillering ability and good panicle exertion. Sheath color of basal leaves is predominantly light purple with a few pure

green plants. Florets have purple apiculi and the grains are medium long. It has a fair degree of tolerance for blast and stem borers. Its grain type and cooking quality are acceptable to local consumers.

VLK Dhan 39 gave an average yield of 3.4 t/ha, compared to 2.6 t/ha for Thapacini (see table). ■

Low temperature injury in some rice varieties

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Unexpected damage in rice variety trials at ARI in early 1981 has been attributed to cold injury. Variety trials were sown the first week of December 1980 and transplanted the first two weeks of January 1981. Seedlings were healthy and green until the beginning of February 1981, when the crop was at maximum tillering. But on 12 February the leaves of some varieties were found to have

turned dark yellow to light red (see table).

The damaged varieties were among entries in different trials. The symptoms were uniform in all replications. One parent is common in the parentage of some damaged varieties.

The symptom was uniform in a complete population of a variety, unlike the symptoms expected from disease, pests or nutritional disorder. Other varieties in the trials were green and healthy. Thus, the phenomenon appeared to be a case of cold injury.

The minimum low temperature was 18.1°C on 10 February and 9.6°C on 11 February. This sudden, extreme drop in temperature probably caused cold injury

Varieties showing low temperature damage at Hyderabad.

Variety	Parentage
IR36	IR1561-228//IR24-4/O.N//CR94-13
IR9828-81-2-3	IR2071-559//IR1820-52//IR36
IR13429-91-2-3	IR4432-53-33//PTB33//IR36
RNR31821	W1263/Tella Hamsa
RNR87877	IR34/Tella Hamsa
RNR98205	RP4-14//RNR29939
RNR99082	IR1514 AE 597/Tella Hamsa
RNR99101	IR1514 AE 597/Tella Hamsa
IET1318	IR139429-196-1
IET6148	Bala/Co 13
IET6228	IET2936//RP79-11//S ₂ S ₂
IET13969	IET1991/W 13801
BR161-28-25	Chandina//IR425-1-1-3-8-3
CR141-5035	N22/TNI//T90//IR8
CR157-22-1900	Vijayai//PTB 10
PK174-13-1-5	Basmati 370//IR95-1-5-3-2-2-2